

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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LITERATURE REVIEW

Extensive research has been conducted on the impact of digital technologies in the field of ecotourism. Among foreign scholars, U. Gretzel, in his study, analyzed how digital transformation is influencing the tourism sector and examined how systems based on digital technologies can provide tailored recommendations to tourists by analyzing their behavior [3]. D. Buhalis, in his research, explored the benefits of smart tourism systems in enhancing tourist experiences and improving efficiency in the tourism industry [4]. M. Svetkoic has conducted scientific work on the application of digital mapping technologies, GIS, and drone technologies in the development of ecotourism [5]. R. Rana analyzed how blockchain technologies can contribute to improving security and transparency in tourism services [6].

In Uzbekistan, scholars such as S. Gulyamov, Kh. Mukhiddinova, U. Turgunov, I. Levakov, T. Rakhmonov, A. Hamdamov, G. Erkayeva, and R. Vayskulov have studied the role of digital marketing and online services in advancing ecotourism in the country. Although the process of digitalization in ecotourism in Uzbekistan has not yet been fully established, the sector holds significant potential for development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on the decrees and resolutions of the President and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan related to the implementation of digital technologies in ecotourism. The research employed induction and deduction, a systematic approach, statistical analysis, and comparative analysis as its primary methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The use of digital and smart technologies in the development of ecotourism is becoming increasingly widespread across different regions of the world. In particular, the countries of the European Union, the United States, and Southeast Asia have successfully implemented projects on digital mapping of ecotourism sites, online services, and blockchain-based secure payment systems. Smart technologies in ecotourism are modern tools designed to ensure environmental protection and promote ecologically responsible tourism. These technologies are applied with the aim of conserving resources, preserving nature, and reducing environmental impacts. Examples include:

Smart devices and sensors – used to monitor the condition of the environment, including air quality, temperature, humidity, and other ecological indicators;

Mobile applications and software – provide tourists with information about safe and environmentally friendly routes, as well as regulations in protected areas to prevent ecological damage;

Biometric monitoring – allows for the assessment and control of tourists' impact on natural environments;

Smart energy systems – optimize energy use through renewable sources such as solar panels and wind turbines, while also regulating consumption;

Artificial intelligence and data analytics – help monitor tourist flows, manage overcrowding in certain locations, and introduce new regulations for sustainable tourism practices.

The application of digital transformations in tourism makes it possible to provide tourists with more convenient services, improve the monitoring of natural areas, and adopt innovative approaches in the development of ecotourism infrastructure. Through digital mapping technologies, tourists can access accurate information about ecological routes, while virtual reality tools allow them to explore destinations in advance. Meanwhile, blockchain technology plays a key role in ensuring the transparency of payment systems and the security of tourism services.

Overall, these technologies not only create comfort and convenience for tourists but also contribute to the efficient use of natural resources and the long-term sustainability of ecotourism. Analyses conducted on the application of digital technologies in Uzbekistan's ecotourism have revealed both the technological opportunities and the existing challenges in this sector [8,9]. While digital technologies can play a crucial role in advancing ecotourism, it is evident that certain obstacles persist in the process

Table 1. Analysis of ecotourism and the implementation of digital technologies in Uzbekistan¹

Direction	Existing Opportunities	Existing Challenges
Digital Mapping	Tourists can find ecological routes online	Internet quality is low in rural areas, and digital services are limited
Virtual Tours	Opportunity to preview ecotourism sites in advance	High-quality virtual tours of Uzbekistan's ecotourism destinations are scarce
Blockchain Technology	Enhances the transparency of tourism payment systems	Low level of acceptance of blockchain among tourists and entrepreneurs
Online Services	Simplifies travel planning and booking	Lack of specialized online platforms dedicated to ecotourism services
Promotion of Ecotourism	Attracts tourists through digital marketing	Uzbekistan's ecotourism potential is insufficiently promoted at the international level

From the table, it is evident that digital technologies create significant opportunities for ecotourism, yet their implementation also faces certain challenges. The main obstacles to the digitalization of ecotourism can be summarized as follows:

Insufficient technological infrastructure – in most ecotourism destinations, internet connectivity remains weak, which complicates the introduction of online services and digital technologies.

Underdeveloped digital services – local ecotourism sites are unable to fully provide tourists with online booking, virtual tours, or access to information through mobile applications.

Lack of investment – financial resources allocated for the implementation of digital technologies are limited, slowing down the overall development process.

At the same time, Uzbekistan possesses unique natural sites that hold great potential for international promotion through digital technologies. In recent years, several state programs have been adopted to support the development of tourism, with particular emphasis on fostering digital ecotourism. In particular, the Resolution “On measures for the development of ecological tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan” outlines action plans and national programs for advancing ecotourism, drawing upon the best practices of developed countries while adapting them to local contexts [2].

Overall, the digitalization process in Uzbekistan's ecotourism is still at an initial stage, with the existing infrastructure remaining underdeveloped. However, by drawing upon international best practices, it is possible to advance ecotourism through the introduction of innovative approaches such as digital mapping, online services, and secure payment systems. Therefore, expanding digital infrastructure at ecotourism sites, training local entrepreneurs in digital service provision, and attracting foreign investment are of critical importance for the sustainable development of this sector.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the role of digital technologies in the development of ecotourism is invaluable. International experience has demonstrated that digital mapping, online services, and blockchain-based secure payment systems are becoming an integral part of popularizing ecotourism destinations and enhancing convenience for tourists. In Uzbekistan, initial steps have already been taken in this direction. However, in order to fully harness the great potential and opportunities available, the following measures are advisable:

Expanding digital infrastructure. It is necessary to improve internet connectivity and expand mobile network coverage in ecotourism destinations. This will enable tourists to fully benefit from digital services

Developing digital mapping systems. Ecotourism sites should be comprehensively mapped and interactive applications for tourists should be created. This will allow tourists to access accurate information on ecological routes, national parks, and protected areas.

Advancing online services. Online booking systems, virtual tours, and mobile applications should be further introduced and enhanced. This will not only increase interest in ecotourism sites but also help adapt services to a digital environment.

Promoting digital marketing and international outreach. To widely promote Uzbekistan's ecotourism potential in the global market, it is important to develop digital marketing strategies. Tourism content should be actively disseminated through social media, websites, and online advertising platforms.

Studying and localizing foreign experience. By learning from the best practices of developed countries in digital ecotourism, innovative solutions can be adapted to the conditions of Uzbekistan and integrated into the local ecotourism sector.

¹ Prepared by the author

Supporting entrepreneurs and local communities. Entrepreneurs and local residents engaged in ecotourism should be trained in the use of digital services, online marketing, and e-commerce. In addition, digital grants and investment programs should be introduced to support small and medium-sized businesses.

Uzbekistan possesses vast untapped potential in the digitalization of ecotourism. The country's rich natural resources, combined with a state policy aimed at promoting tourism, provide a strong foundation for accelerating these processes. By integrating innovative technologies into ecotourism, not only will favorable conditions for tourists be created, but ecological sustainability will also be ensured. Therefore, pursuing digital transformation as a strategic priority will make a significant contribution to the long-term development of ecotourism.

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